

Rac-4b

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-163-rac-20%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	9	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 2 163 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/26/2021 9:50:41 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/26/2021 10:19:54 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.778	1409690	49.80	145242
2	8.042	1420756	50.20	118521

Asy-4b

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-164-1-20%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	29	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 2 164 1
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/26/2021 10:08:36 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/26/2021 10:22:25 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.802	539205	2.79	56018
2	8.057	18780436	97.21	1625292